

milieu
 women disability and inclusion

Women, Disability, and Inclusion – Scientific Excellence in Bulgaria
 GA No. 952369

Deliverable 6.7

Final project conference successfully organised and results presented to relevant audiences

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Authors:	Lyuba Spasova
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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable reports the successful organisation of the final MILIEU conference, where the project's results were effectively presented to pertinent audiences.

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1. The conference

For the third year in a row, the MILIEU project team and the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences hosted an international conference in Sofia. The 2023 conference was held on November 24-26, with the theme "Gender, Disability, and Social Change." The conference's goal was to examine various aspects of women's rights, the disability movement, and LGBTQI+ empowerment, as well as to provide insights into the challenges that transformative movements face.

The event explored a wide range of topics, including arts and media, social policies and legislation, case studies, activism, and opposition to progressive initiatives. The impact of the arts, literature, theatre, and music on challenging stereotypes was discussed, as well as the role of pop culture, film, television, and social media in reshaping perceptions of gender and disability. Existing social policies and legislation affecting marginalised groups were evaluated, with a focus on reform opportunities. The conference highlighted successful initiatives, best practices, and case studies that contribute to the advancement of gender and disability rights. Activists shared their stories, emphasising the difficulties, successes, and future directions of transformative movements.

The event facilitated discussions on various forms of backlash and organised mobilisation against social change movements, addressing the role of political and religious opportunism and populism in creating a hostile environment. Researchers, activists, artists, policymakers, and other interested parties were actively involved in the discussion, sharing insights, research findings, success stories, and creative expressions. The conference made an important contribution to the ongoing discussion about gender, disability, and social change by providing a platform for revealing transformations, fostering inclusivity, and amplifying voices in these critical areas. This event's shared experiences and ideas are expected to have a long-term impact on future discussions and endeavours.

The highly successful conference attracted a large audience and served as a dissemination event for the project, its results, and achievements. In 2023, a number of other larger and smaller dissemination events, such as the one coinciding with the summer school in Borovets in June and the one in Brussels in December, were held. The international conference, on the other hand, has an unrivalled audience and coverage.

The international conference also provided an excellent opportunity for MILIEU to make new contacts and generate ideas for potential partnerships and initiatives.

2. Organisation

The conference call for papers was distributed to all major networks (mail and social media) relevant to the topic (10 000 people were reached). The good coverage of the call for papers resulted in the receipt of over 50 applications. The excellent turnout was also aided by the partial PhD Grant that was offered- accommodation for two nights for selected ESRs.

37 talks were approved and included in the programme, and the programme was extended by one day to accommodate all participants on time (the conference was originally scheduled to take place on November 24th and 25th).

There were two keynote speakers invited:

- Teodor Mladenov (University of Dundee, Scotland) - Social Change and Disability
- Luca Gloria Vázquez Rodríguez (University College London, UK) is a researcher at the University of London. - Objects of Desire, Victims, or Empowered Subjects: Women in the Media in the Twenty-First Century.

The conference attendees represented institutions from 14 and 21 countries, respectively.

The conference was held in fully hybrid mode on the 24th and 25th of November and online on the 26th of November.

3. Photos and videos

Photos of all participants were taken upon consent and uploaded on social media at the spot. With the authors' permission, the majority of the videos of the in-person talks were uploaded to the MILIEU YouTube channel and the project website.

The venue for the conference was selected specifically for the suitability to host a hybrid event and for the production of HD quality videos of the presentations.

Institute of Philosophy and Sociology at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences

“Gender, Disability and Social Change” International Conference

24-26 November 2023

Launchee, Kepler 452B Hall | TSUM, 2 Knyaginya Maria Luiza Blvd., Sofia | <https://maps.app.goo.gl/U17rRci8pMExxqQH6>

Zoom link for online/hybrid access (Registration is required):

<https://us02web.zoom.us/meeting/register/tZMRcuusrDIqEtYp8icJUOXPIlHKaR26Khrq>

PROGRAM

Please note all hours are in Eastern European Time - EET (UTC+2).

24 November 2023 (FRIDAY)

09:00 - 09:30 – Registration (also during the day)

09:30 - 09:45 – Welcome and Introductory Remarks

Emilia Chengelova, Lyuba Spasova, Liisa Hanninen, Shaban Darakchi

09:45 - 11:00 – KEYNOTE LECTURE

Teodor Mladenov (University of Dundee, United Kingdom) - Disability and Social Change

11:00 - 11:15 – Coffee break

11:15 - 12:45 – PANEL 1

Chair: Olga Kolotouchkina (Complutense University of Madrid, Spain)

Esther Leyre Marín Álvarez (Complutense University of Madrid, Spain) – User Experience of People with Visual Disabilities: Accessibility and Neuroscience

Mohammed Faheem Kottur Valiyapediakal Mannisseri (Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, India) – Knowledge and Power: Ableist Discourse in Textbooks

Célia Bouchet (Sciences Po, France) and Natacha Guay (University Toulouse Jean Jaurès, France) - Sex and Couple Life of People with Disabilities in France: Policy Shortcomings and Roads for Improvements

Hanan JR Alawna (University of Szeged, Hungary) - Art as a Channel for Women's Voice: Marjane Satrapi's Graphic Novel Persepolis as a Model

12:45 - 14:15 – Lunch

14:15 - 15:45 – PANEL 2

Chair: Liisa Hänninen (Complutense University of Madrid, Spain)

Shaban Darakchi (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria): Standing Against Gender Based Violence in Bulgaria: The Case of Debora

Lorraine Hayman (University of Galway, Ireland) - Gender-Binary Phraseology and Accounting for Harms in Ireland's Legal Approach to Image-Based Sexual Abuse

Emna Sfaihi (University of Debrecen, Hungary) – Precarity and Social Change in Age of Iron by J.M. Coetzee

Yoana Pavlova (Technical University of Sofia, Bulgaria) – Fashion – a Path to Patriarchy

15:45 - 16:00 – Coffee break

16:00 – 17:45 - PANEL 3

Chair: Ralitsa Dimitrova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

Mila Stancheva (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria) – Business Models for Social Causes: Good Practices and Controversies Around Social Enterprises in Bulgaria and Brazil

Mina Kostova (Bulgarian Association of Science, Bulgaria) – Gender Representation and Censorship in Sex Educational and Children Literature in Bulgaria

Bukurie Ozuni (University of Genoa, Italy) – Local Authorities' Role in Fostering Equity, Inclusion, and Social Transformation: The Italian Perspective

Martina Arcadu (University of Genoa, Italy) – Gender, care, and food practices: activism for community resilience

Georgina Holmes (The Open University, UK) - (Invisible) staff: Business continuity, organisational survival and resilience in the UN system during crisis

17:45– 18:00 – Closing Discussion for Day 1

25 NOVEMBER 2023 (SATURDAY)

09:00 – 10:00 – Lyuba Spasova - MILIEU: a success story. Results and outcomes of the project

10:00 – 11:15 – KEYNOTE LECTURE

Lucía Gloria Vázquez Rodríguez (University College London, UK) - Objects of Desire, Victims or Empowered Subjects: Media Representations of Women in the 21st Century

11:15 – 11:30 Coffee break

11:30 – 13:00 PANEL 4

Chair: Aleksandra Traykova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

Melisa Campana (Complutense University of Madrid, Spain) – Legal, Safe And Free Abortion In The Southern Cone: The End Point Of A Long Feminist Struggle

Ralitsa Dimitrova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria) – Anti-gender Campaigns and LGBTQI+ Minorities in Bulgaria: Attacks and Resistance

Jacqueline Shaw (University of Sussex, UK) – Healing Justice as Radical Approach to Feminist Activism

Lyuba Spasova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria) – Discourses of hatred: the protests against the screenings of “Close”

13:00 - 14:30 – Lunch

14:30 - 16:00 – PANEL 5 (Hybrid session)

Chair: Martina Drobenova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

Aleksandra Traykova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria) – Are We Opposing Social Change? Anti-gender Campaigns and Violence Against Women in Bulgaria

Marie Astier (Université d'Artois, France) – “An Attempt Almost Like Any Other”: An Obviously Non-freak Show

Aytalina Kulichkina (University of Vienna, Austria) – The Political Contention of LGBTQ+ Communities in the Digital Age - State of the Art, Limitations, and Opportunities for Comparative Research

Mitul Joseph Koickakudy (CHRIST Deemed to be University, India) - Fememe Fetal - Understanding the Representation of Women in Indian Political Memes

16:00 – 16:15 – Coffee break

16:15 - 17:45 – PANEL 6 (Hybrid session)

Chair: Mira Dobрева (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

Ana María Rio Poncela (University of Cantabria, Spain), **Mateusz Smieszek** (Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Poland) – Videos on YouTube as a Learning Tool About Sexuality, Motherhood, and Upbringing by People with Intellectual Disabilities. A Collective Case Study from Spain and Poland

Agnese Pellay (Università degli studi di Padova, Italy) – Challenges, Issues and Perspectives of Independent Living in the Veneto Region: A Case Study Conducted Within a Cooperative in the Alta Padovana Area

Maria Giulia Pascariello (Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro, Italy) – Gender, Disability, Migration Background. An Intersectional Reading of Educational Contexts

Paula Garcia-Rodriguez (University of Seville, Spain) – The ‘Bridgerton’ Question: Female Voices and Gender Expectations in the Regency Fiction

17:45 - 18:00 – Closing Discussion for Day 2

26 NOVEMBER 2023 (SUNDAY)

09:00 - 10:30 – PANEL 7 (Session entirely online)

Chair: Lyuba Spasova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

Sidra Abbas (Virtual University of Pakistan, Pakistan) – Portraying the Gendered Image of Nursing in Electronic Media of Pakistan

Baby Rizwana N V (Independent Researcher, Malappuram, India) – Film “Margarita with a Straw” (2014): Linking Disability, Accessibility and Sexuality

Yiqi Hu (College of Humanities and Development Studies, China Agricultural University, China) – Seeing the Gender of Disabled Bodies: Rights Protection and Social Support Issues for Disabled Women – Evidence from China

Lyuboslava Kostova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria) - Disability between Vulnerability and Empowerment: Inspirations for Feminist Social Research

10:30 - 11:00 – Break

11:00 - 12:30 – PANEL 8 (Session entirely online)

Chair: Aleksandra Traykova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

Swastika Suresh Bhat (Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Dubai, UAE) – Evolving Gender Stereotypes in the Digital Age: An Analysis of Viral Content on TikTok and Instagram Reels

Evelin Barney (Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Dubai, UAE) – The Impact of Using Tik Tok Beauty Filters on the Body Image/Self-Esteem of University Students

Muskan Vinod Bhatia (Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Dubai, UAE) – Cinematic Influence on Gender Stereotypes: A Comprehensive Analysis of Contemporary Hollywood Cinema and Its Effect on Young Adults' Perceptions

Parth Joshi (Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Dubai, UAE) – Sludge Content and Its Impact on the Gen Z Attention Span

12:30 - 13:00 – Break

13:00 - 14:30 – PANEL 9 (Session entirely online)

Chair: Shaban Darakchi (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

Clara Sánchez-Rebato Valiente (Complutense University of Madrid, Spain) – Identifying with the Main Character of a Fantasy Story: How Disability Is Discussed on Booktube. The Case Study of Sarah-Jane Bird

Natalie Byfield (St. John's University, USA) – Surveilling the Boundaries of a Black Man's Sanity

Ilayda Ustel (The Ohio State University, USA) – How LGBTQ+ Became “A National Security Threat”: Turkey's Anti-LGBTQ+ Rhetoric

Ying Tan (Beijing Language and Culture University, China) – Feminist Translation into Spanish of Sexist Scenes Characterized by the Male Gaze of LIU Cixin's the Three-Body Trilogy

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**“GENDER, DISABILITY AND SOCIAL CHANGE”
MILIEU INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE**

24-26 November 2023, Sofia

ABSTRACT BOOKLET

**INSTITUTE
OF PHILOSOPHY
AND SOCIOLOGY**

**Università
di Genova**

**UNIVERSIDAD
COMPLUTENSE
MADRID**

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GENDER, DISABILITY AND SOCIAL CHANGE

MILIEU INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE, SOFIA, 24.11.2023 – 26.11.2023

In an era marked by groundbreaking social change, we find ourselves amidst a wave of transformative movements. From the resurgent fight for gender equality and LGBTQI+ rights to the ongoing disability movement, society is evolving at a pace unseen before. The push for inclusivity, representation, and empowerment is echoing through various spheres of life.

In recent times, we have witnessed remarkable strides in advancing women's rights, empowering sexual communities, and championing the disability movement. On the other hand, we have been witnessing a backlash coming from right-wing actors that oppose and often ridicule these changes and aim to overturn and shut down different policies, movements and inspiring practices and examples.

This conference aims to explore and explain these evolving landscapes and provide a dynamic platform that aims to explore how transformation in gender and disability is actively shaped.

24 NOVEMBER 2023 (FRIDAY)

11:15 - 12:45 – PANEL 1

User Experience of People with Visual Disabilities: Accessibility and Neuroscience

Esther Leyre Marín Álvarez (Complutense University of Madrid, Spain)

The web, conceived in 1997 as universally accessible, still presents obstacles for users with diverse abilities. Although interactions in digital environments have improved the quality of life for many people, it remains a source of limitations and frustrations, up to twice as much for users with total visual impairment. This research emphasizes the need to provide methodologies and tools that consider users with different abilities in all stages and from the beginning of design, redesign and development of digital products and services, directly collecting their needs and goals on the web, delving into their reactions and emotions.

The study focuses on individuals with total visual impairment, combining declarative techniques - focus groups-, observational methods -user testing-, and neuroscientific approaches -GSR, Heart Rate-, to gather their experiences while navigating the web, along with the impact on their behavior and decision-making, providing a comprehensive user-focused approach that covers both conscious and subconscious dimensions. The findings will culminate in the creation of a Persona profile for users with Total Visual Impairment, which will guide designers and developers in creating accessible, usable, and satisfying digital products and services, promoting inclusion and equitable access in the digital environment. Furthermore, this study will contribute to understanding the relationship between accessibility guidelines and real user needs. Ultimately, all users will benefit from better experiences and optimized websites, while organizations will expand their target audience, optimize resources, and improve their outcomes. Finally, society will enjoy higher levels of inclusion, equal opportunities, and universal accessibility.

Knowledge and Power: Ableist Discourse in Textbooks

Mohammed Faheem Kottur Valiyapediakal Mannisseri (Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, India)

The knowledge imparted through curriculum creates a fundamental awareness of the social world, which forms part of the cultural memory of a society. The question is, which knowledge is considered worth teaching? Whose knowledge is represented in the curriculum? Most academic knowledge gets produced/reproduced through the curriculum in general and the textbook in particular. In the process of this, several ideas remain alien to texts. This research exposes the cultural stereotypes and dominant discourses reproduced through the textbook in different forms. Taking a cue from Foucault, the study will explore the knowledge-power equation that gets reflected and reinforced in textbooks. The main focus is the discourse analysis of the SCERT (State Council of Research and Training) Keralapatavali textbooks (Patavali is the Malayalam term for curriculum; Keralapatavali translates to Kerala Curriculum). While it is acknowledged that textbooks are not immune to the power dynamics of caste, class, gender, and sexuality, this research primarily examines the nature of knowledge produced and disseminated through texts through the paradigms of ableism and the disability discourse. This work seeks to thoroughly understand how disability is constructed and perpetuated through educational

materials, contributing to the existing literature on disability studies and to the field of sociology of knowledge. By synthesizing different perspectives, the study aims to reveal the complex dynamics of ideology, knowledge, power, and discourse that perpetuate ableism in our society. This research exposes the misrepresentation and mistreatment of disability discourse stemming from longstanding ableist knowledge systems.

Sex and Couple Life of People with Disabilities in France: Policy Shortcomings and Roads for Improvements

Célia Bouchet (Sciences Po, France) and **Natacha Guay** (University Toulouse Jean Jaurès, France)

A classic typology of disability policies distinguishes between two models: the social protection model, focused on a medical understanding of disability, and the rights model, which adopts a social perspective (Heyer, 2002). While the former faces growing criticism, social rights, like social minimums or compensation benefit, are crucial for realizing disability human rights (Revillard, 2018). Yet, their gender-specific impacts, particularly in areas related to bodywork (Twigg, 2000), remain largely unexplored. To what extent can French social policies, such as disability-related social minimums or disability compensation, alleviate obstacles in the sexual and couple lives of individuals who have grown up with disabilities, considering gender? Drawing from two interview-based studies conducted in France involving 38 women, 29 men, and 2 non-binary individuals, all living with conditions like cerebral palsy, muscular dystrophy, visual impairments, or specific learning difficulties, it becomes evident that current policies fall short. Disability-related social minimums offer limited assistance and, in some cases, perpetuate dependence due to household-based calculations, affecting individuals with disabilities of all genders. This contrasts with the gendered economic dependence predominantly experienced by women in the general population. Moreover, except for a politically engaged minority among male respondents, the potential of compensation benefits to address the lack of access to sexual and couple facets (e.g., funding for a caregiver to assist with masturbation) is largely overlooked. Recent changes in French public policies hint at possible roads for improvements.

Art as a Channel for Women's Voice: Marjane Satrapi's Graphic Novel *Persepolis* as a Model

Hanan JR Alawna (University of Szeged, Hungary)

The twenty first century is best described as a melting pot in which people all over the world could influence and being influenced by each other simultaneously. However, globalization of the world and its becoming a small village result into two opposing poles. On the one pole, there is multiculturalism which means the preservation of various cultures within the same society. On the other pole, there is interculturalism which indicates the blending of one culture into another which, in turn, could result in identity crisis, fragmentation and instability. In light of this scene, the present research aims to discuss the traumatic experience that Satrapi as an Oriental woman has to undergo when she leaves her country Iran to pursuit her studies in Vienna. This change of place creates an identity crisis for Satrapi. Thus, in *Persepolis* (2000-2003), the protagonist is confused whether to indulge in the new culture, that is a Western one or to keep her Oriental Iranian roots. However, during this traumatic experience, the protagonist seizes the chance to correct some misconceptions about both the West and the East using graphics. Thus, the research traces the graphics in Satrapi's graphic novel to reflect on her traumatic experience and the way she employs art as a means to communicate her trauma with the reader.

14:15 - 15:45 – PANEL 2

Standing Against Gender Based Violence in Bulgaria: The Case of Debora

Shaban Darakchi (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

In July 2023, the story of 18-year-old Debora, who was tortured by her intimate partner with a box cutter, resulting in 400 stitches, prompted an unprecedented public uproar and sparked enormous rallies throughout numerous towns in Bulgaria. This study investigates the broader context of Bulgaria's anti-gender campaigns, which tend to underestimate the severity of gender-based violence, and poses the intriguing question of why other incidents of violence against women, including murders, failed to elicit comparable public reactions.

This study tries to identify the driving elements behind the unusual response to Debora's case through a thorough investigation of socioeconomic and political issues. The paper seeks to shed light on the underlying mechanisms that compel the public to rise against a specific case of gender-based violence by analyzing the unique dynamics at play, unraveling the complex interplay of societal, political, and economic elements that galvanized these protests in support of Debora and, by extension, in condemnation of gender-based violence as a whole.

Gender-Binary Phraseology and Accounting for Harms in Ireland's Legal Approach to Image-Based Sexual Abuse

Lorraine Hayman (University of Galway, Ireland)

In this presentation, I share how Ireland's Harassment, Harmful Communications and Related Offences Act (HHCRO) fails to capture the harms of Image-Based Sexual Abuse (IBSA) synthesised from existing literature. I consider two Research Questions: (1) What does existing literature say about the harms of IBSA? (2) To what extent does the HHCRO account for these harms? Through reviewing 130 pieces of the literature identified through keyword/phrase searches on online databases, I establish that the harms of IBSA are multiple, including (1) Physical harm, (2) Psychological harm, (3) Interpersonal/social harm, (4) Harm to sexual autonomy, (5) Economic harm, (6) Harm to safety, freedom, and privacy, and (7) Harm to society. On critically analysing HHCRO, I find it does not account for the extent of the harm caused by IBSA. HHCRO lacks a victim-survivor-centric approach to harm, fails to reflect an embodied understanding of harm, and does not approach harm from an intersectional perspective. Notably, the gender-binary phraseology in HHCRO is also potentially harmful. Using the gender binary 'he or she, his or her' excludes gender non-confirming individuals who identify as they/them or other non-binary pronouns. The binary language in HHCRO is not sensitive to concerns that transgender women and gender-nonconforming individuals can experience more online harassment and abuse than cis-gendered women. My recommendations to redress these limitations include familiarising the judiciary with feminist legal approaches and utilising victim-survivor-centric and intersectional lenses in applying HHCRO and legal reform. I contribute a critical feminist analysis of Irish legislation to emerging IBSA scholarship.

Precarity and Social Change in *Age of Iron* by J.M. Coetzee

Emna Sfaihi (University of Debrecen, Hungary)

In *Age of Iron* by the South African writer J.M. Coetzee, a cancer-ridden female scholar and protagonist Mrs. Curren is confronted with the brutalities of the Apartheid regime. In an individual attempt to stand against the oppressive system, she decides to give a hand to a crippled and homeless male figure Mr. Vercueil. In this paper, I investigate the seemingly innocuous practices of care relying on Vrinda Dalmiya's article "Vulnerability, Precarity and the Ambivalent Intervention of Empathic Care" in *Care Ethics in the Age of Precarity* edited by Maurice Hamington and Michael Flower. My aim is to show how ambivalent is the white female stance and how difficult it is to relate to the disabled other through empathic care. In the final section, I will highlight the best practices Mrs. Curren comes up with to make a difference in a worn-out individual and a war-torn country.

Fashion – a Path to Patriarchy

Yoana Pavlova (Technical University of Sofia, Bulgaria)

The age of technology has changed not only the way we live but also the way we perceive ourselves. Social media, pop culture, and advertising set the "successful" model for us to aspire to. This "successful model" focuses primarily on appearance, making the body the primary expresser of the individual. A 'fashion' of dress and behaviour is imposed that as much individualises as it uniformises the personality. Norms are set which, however, embody double standards towards women and men. This study shows what are the key elements of a 'successful' woman in relation to the fashion imposed and how they relate to traditional notions of femininity.

16:00 – 17:45 - PANEL 3

Business Models for Social Causes: Good Practices and Controversies Around Social Enterprises in Bulgaria and Brazil

Mila Stancheva (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

Exploring business models and integrating different types of economic activities in their work, i. e. the pursuit of their social missions, seems to become more and more popular among civil society organizations (CSOs) in Bulgaria, and not only. Social entrepreneurship is one option and in the recent years it is gaining significant attention - especially from Bulgarian CSOs operating in the social sphere, but also from "green", educational and many other kinds of organizations, including (re)granting organizations, as well as from researchers, business companies, policy makers.

The presentation will be based on the findings from a recently completed doctoral study (2022), conducted in Bulgaria and Sao Paulo, Brazil, and on some new observations and will focus not only on good examples for social entrepreneurial initiatives aiming to push the social and economic integration of people with disabilities and experiencing psychic difficulties, but also on some controversial aspects emerging as a result of these dynamics between private and common interest and of the model's practical implementation – aiming at economic success and at the same time preserving the engaged vulnerable people's physical and psychical well-being; the problematic

relations between social enterprises and local and national institutions; the motivation behind starting such an initiative in the first place and so on.

Gender Representation and Censorship in Sex Educational and Children Literature in Bulgaria

Mina Kostova (Bulgarian Association of Science, Bulgaria)

The representation of sex education in children's books in Bulgaria, and the possible political influences that may want to imply certain understandings around sex, gender and homosexuality specifically in the Bulgarian context. Through primary and secondary data, the research explores the strategies that publishers have to offer more diverse and sex-positive content on the Bulgarian market, how political radicals and conservative parties influence popular representations of sexuality in modern Bulgaria, and the extent to which this influence shapes the Bulgarian general public's understanding of sex education in books. The research hypothesizes that publishing houses practice self-censorship because of the lack in demand for more diverse sex educational books, and that there are homophobic political practices and anti-gender campaigns that influence the Bulgarian society. Findings from the research indicate that there is a gap in academic literature about sex education in books consequently of the struggles of gender based studies in academia and publicly, that books that tackle sensitive topics regarding sex education and heavily connected to publishers personal responsibilities, and that political activism against books continues, leading to a limited understanding of sex education in the Bulgarian context.

Local Authorities' Role in Fostering Equity, Inclusion, and Social Transformation: The Italian Perspective

Bukurie Ozuni (University of Genoa, Italy)

In Italy, local authorities are pivotal in addressing gender equality, disability rights, and societal transformation. This article systematically examines their multifaceted responsibilities, including providing essential services and crafting policies for equity and inclusion. Drawing from academic literature and governmental reports, we explore three key themes.

First, local authorities in Italy are at the forefront of promoting gender equality, establishing safe havens for gender-based violence survivors, enacting workplace equity policies, and running public awareness campaigns.

Second, these authorities engineer an inclusive society by ensuring accessible public spaces, providing support services for individuals with disabilities, and advocating for their full participation. Lastly, local authorities act as catalysts for social change by funding grassroots organizations, developing comprehensive frameworks for equity and justice, and building trust-based relationships with marginalized communities.

This paper examines the challenges facing gender, disability, and societal change in Italy and how local authorities are addressing them. It highlights innovative strategies and initiatives employed by local authorities, such as establishing safe havens for survivors of gender-based violence, enacting policies to promote workplace parity, and advocating accessibility standards and inclusive policies for people with disabilities. In addition, the article examines the role of local authorities in fostering social change through funding grassroots organizations, developing comprehensive frameworks for equity and justice, and building trust-based relationships with marginalized communities. The inquiry concludes by emphasizing the indispensable role of local authorities in Italy's quest for gender equality, disability rights, and societal transformation.

Gender, care, and food practices: activism for community resilience

Martina Arcadu (University of Genoa, Italy)

In an era of growing uncertainty, women are emerging as key figures in addressing crisis situations through community care contexts, emphasizing the importance of traditionally assigned gender roles. These roles, deeply rooted in social and cultural narratives, form the fabric of shared social representations. Women's groups, often stemming from pre-existing networks, stand as vital resources during emergencies, providing a crucial informal service often implicitly included in reconstruction policies. Their proactive engagement is based on an understanding of daily realities and caters to the specific needs of the reference community.

However, women's participation has historically been confined to the private and domestic sphere, with an emphasis on household management, including food preparation. Currently, women-led social movements focused on food-related issues and meeting basic needs are gaining importance, creating spaces for activism and resistance (e.g., South American "ollas comunes"). These spaces recognize food as a central symbol and serve as grounds for addressing immediate needs, sharing ideas, knowledge, and promoting community resilience.

Despite significant challenges, such as legitimacy and social integration, these movements are evolving and organizing, becoming essential community mechanisms for social support and community resilience. This contribution aims to critically reflect on these unique gender activism spaces, recognizing them as essential components to tackle contemporary challenges and shape a more resilient future through food practices. The innovative actions carried out by these groups foster the creation of tangible and social structures, inspired by the protection and resistance characteristic of the ethics of female care.

(Invisible) staff: Business continuity, organisational survival and resilience in the UN system during crisis

Georgina Holmes (The Open University, UK)

Scholars have shown that international organisations (IOs) rarely die but they are none the less preoccupied with their survival. Recent threats to the liberal international order have exposed the fragility of IOs, leading to renewed interest in understanding how IOs respond to political contestation, financial uncertainty, fears of legitimacy depletion and state withdrawal. Until now, the relationship between business continuity management, IO survival and individual employees has been overlooked in the literature on international administrative bureaucracies, international organisations and international relations theory. Adopting a feminist postcolonial theoretical approach and drawing on 30 in-depth interviews and a global-wide survey with over 100 staff across 52 agencies and offices, this paper examines how the UN system bureaucracy continued to function in the first 18 months of the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, the paper critically analyses staff perceptions of their experiences of operating in UN 'virtual offices' between March 2020 and August 2021, when the UN Secretary General called for a system-wide adoption of the Alternative Working Arrangements Directive. The paper undertakes a bottom-up analysis of the gendered and raced practices of business continuity, and the effects these processes have on staff themselves, in particular staff groups that felt more vulnerable or isolated during the pandemic.

25 NOVEMBER 2023 (SATURDAY)

11:30 – 13:00 PANEL 4

Legal, Safe And Free Abortion In The Southern Cone: The End Point Of A Long Feminist Struggle

Melisa Campana (Complutense University of Madrid, Spain)

Having access to legal, safe and free abortion is one of the main demands of feminists' movements in the Southern Cone. Articulated since the 2000s by the National Campaigns to the Right of Legal Abortion, this demand accompanies social protests and it's also included in the collective "Not One[Woman] Less" (Ni Una Menos in Spanish). Banners, graffiti and the green handkerchiefs are icons of this struggle, despite the fact that the legal proposals did not manage to advance in the countries' Congresses until 2012, when Uruguay had the first successful normative, followed by Chile (2017) and Argentina (2020); while Brazil is currently debating similar bills. The feminist and human rights movements that has fought for years for the legalisation of abortion throughout the Southern Cone (the so-called "green tide") has driven important advances, but the risk of reversals remains in the region, where neo-conservative and extreme right-wing proposals seem to be gaining ground. The main purpose of this paper is to map the progresses and challenges in terms of access to legal, safe and free abortion, paying special attention to the role that social movements and especially feminist organisations have played in the achievement and defence of this and other rights that are crucial for a dignified life in supposedly democratic regimes.

Anti-gender Campaigns and LGBTQI+ Minorities in Bulgaria: Attacks and Resistance

Ralitsa Dimitrova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

The text discusses the alarming rise of anti-gender campaigns, particularly targeting LGBTQI+ minorities. These campaigns have gained momentum by importing transnational anti-LGBTQI+ rhetoric and adapting it to fit specific national contexts. Some scholars categorize these efforts as anti-LGBTQI+ movements. In Bulgaria, where anti-gender campaigns have surfaced prominently, sexual minorities face strategic attacks from multiple sources:

Evangelical organizations affiliated with specific religious and political entities in the USA.

Nationalist populist actors within the country.

Public figures and media outlets with strong connections to Russian foreign politics and propaganda.

To comprehensively investigate these campaigns' strategies and discourses aimed at LGBTQI+ individuals in Bulgaria, this presentation summarizes 12 case studies covering public campaigns spanning from 2018 to 2023. The study has three primary objectives:

Analyze Discourses and Rhetoric: The research seeks to outline the primary discourses and rhetorical patterns employed against LGBTQI+ individuals. This analysis takes a comparative, transnational perspective, shedding light on how these campaigns adapt globally circulating ideas to local contexts.

Identify Key Actors and Dynamics: By scrutinizing the mobilization capacities and cooperation among various actors, the study aims to identify the key individuals and organizations involved in anti-LGBTQI+ campaigns. Understanding the dynamics between these actors is essential for addressing the issue effectively.

Explore Resistance Strategies: Lastly, the study delves into the strategies employed by LGBTQI+ organizations and collectives to resist these campaigns. Examining the resilience of these communities is vital in countering the discriminatory efforts against them.

In summary, this research sheds light on the disturbing trend of anti-gender campaigns, specifically targeting LGBTQI+ minorities in Bulgaria. By analyzing rhetoric, identifying actors, and exploring resistance strategies, the study aims to contribute to a better understanding of this issue and potentially inform countermeasures to protect the rights and well-being of LGBTQI+ individuals.

Healing Justice as Radical Approach to Feminist Activism

Jacqueline Shaw (University of Sussex, UK)

Tackling gender inequality and gender-based violence is a compelling priority for feminist movements globally. Yet, many feminist activists are motivated by their own traumatic experiences. They also face risks due to both their identities, and their actions defending rights, especially in countries facing repressive gender backlash.

Healing justice is an emerging political organising strategy that directly addresses this issue, by prioritising collective healing as an essential aspect of activism. This was the rationale for an exploratory research project - collaboratively led by the Institute of Development Studies (IDS), UAF-Africa and the Feminist Republik. We asked i) ‘what Healing Justice means to feminist activists and holistic healers in different African contexts’; and ii) ‘how pathways to collective healing could evolve and be supported’. African research teams in DRC, Senegal and South Africa conducted semi-structured interviews with feminist activists and holistic healers, which were supplemented by regional interviews, and two learning events.

We found evidence of collective trauma rooted in oppressive histories, intergenerational trauma, and structural violence, which manifested in negative physical, mental–emotional, and spiritual effects; and we identified how activism environments can amplify these impacts and create vicious cycles of decreasing wellbeing if systemic harms are not addressed. Most importantly, we built an embryonic framework to guide operationalisation of collective healing processes. This weaves together diverse healing modalities, creative, visual and performative approaches, and political organising practices. Whilst, Healing justice should be contextualised, we will illustrate how processes might unfold to generate more nurturing, inclusive, sustainable and effective feminist organising.

Discourses of hatred: the protests against the screenings of “Close”

Lyuba Spasova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

The paper undertakes an in-depth examination of hate crimes, with a particular emphasis on the concerning incidents of right-wing protests that occurred during screenings of the film "Close" in Bulgaria. Hate crimes have emerged as an escalating global issue, taking on diverse manifestations such as symbolic violence and demonstrations targeting cultural and artistic expressions. The objective of this study is to provide insight into the complex dynamics of these occurrences, elucidating the underlying motivations and resulting consequences.

This study utilizes a comprehensive methodology to analyse the origins and expressions of hate crimes within the framework of right-wing demonstrations in response to a film that addresses contentious social matters. Through the application of content analysis on media representations and video footage, this study aims to discern recurring patterns, ideologies, and underlying factors that contribute to the emergence and sustenance of these phenomena.

The research presented in this paper provides valuable insights into the current scholarly conversation on hate crimes. It offers a nuanced comprehension of the particular interpretations that justify acts of hate-induced violence. These interpretations manifest as explicit verbal expressions that highlight the breakdown of shared meanings, ultimately fueling violence by legitimising and facilitating such actions.

14:30 - 16:00 – PANEL 5 (Hybrid session)

Are We Opposing Social Change? Anti-gender Campaigns and Violence Against Women in Bulgaria

Aleksandra Traykova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

In 2018, Bulgaria declined to sign the Istanbul Convention amid an unprecedented instance of mass gay and trans panic that portrayed the convention's use of the term "gender" as unconstitutional and a gateway to embracing "gender ideology". Since then, the EU's poorest state has struggled to come up with adequate measures against domestic violence despite an increasing number of femicides. This paper highlights the links between "anti-gender" campaigns and gender-based violence, including the structural violence encountered by Bulgarian women who require institutional help in order to leave aggressive partners. It showcases the way figures of political authority in Bulgaria are willing to sacrifice the safety of female citizens in order to oppose the more general efforts to promote equality between all sexes, genders and sexual orientations. As a consequence, abused women's basic human needs are not met and their rights are continuously trampled, because instead of responding adequately to instances of violence, institutions keep reinforcing toxic social dynamics and contributing to a hostile social climate that opposes progressive ideas. In conclusion, "anti-gender" campaigns reproduce a perpetual vicious cycle of isolation, disempowerment, inequality and injustice by means of applying sexist notions that hinder Bulgarian women's struggle for survival and independence.

"An Attempt Almost Like Any Other": An Obviously Non-freak Show

Marie Astier (Université d'Artois, France)

I'm excited to submit a communication proposal to the "Arts and Expression" strand of the "Gender, Disability, and Social Change" international conference.

In 2018, I defended a thesis in performing arts called "presence and representation of mental disability on the French contemporary stage". Since then, I have pursued my research focusing on all types of disability, using the same methodology, inspired by disability studies. I especially study performances played by actors and actresses with disabilities, in which disability becomes an aesthetic resource regarding dramaturgy, playing and staging.

My presentation focuses on the theatre play *An attempt almost like any other* (*Une tentative presque comme une autre*), by the twins Papachristou. This play is performed by Clément, as "abled" gay person and associated artist at the National Theater of Brussels, and Guillaume, a "disabled" bisexual person, living in Marseille where he practices theater and dance as an amateur. I argue that, by speaking and dancing together and with the audience, Clément and Guillaume ostensibly distance the performance from the traditional "freak shows". The latter treat spectators as uninitiated consumers

taking pleasure in being fooled, and who are offered the opportunity to observe “creatures” radically different from themselves. In contrast, Clément and Guillaume offer a funny, sensitive and festive encounter that challenges stereotypes and fosters inclusion. The analysis of this show is therefore an opportunity to explore the artistic and scenic for fostering inclusivity, representation, and empowerment by combining issues related to gender and to disability.

The Political Contention of LGBTQ+ Communities in the Digital Age - State of the Art, Limitations, and Opportunities for Comparative Research

Aytalina Kulichkina (University of Vienna, Austria)

This paper serves two purposes: It establishes an analytical framework for conducting comparative research on political contention in the digital age and offers a review of social media research related to LGBTQ+ political contention. There is a lack of systematic insights into the literature concerning digitally-mediated LGBTQ+ political contention and its potential for comparative research. To address this gap, we employ a scoping literature review focusing on key comparative dimensions such as political context, social media, and knowledge production.

The following research questions guide our review: What comparative dimensions can be employed to construct an analytical framework for studying political contention in the digital age? To what extent does the existing literature examine and focus on these dimensions?

First, a contextual dimension comprises constraints and opportunities for digital LGBTQ+ contention: (a) the demarcated political or cultural contexts that influence, incentivize, or restrict political activism and (b) the specific affordances of social media platforms that shape different forms of political contention.

The second dimension centers on the two levels of action: (a) the process of knowledge production, encompassing the ways research on digital LGBTQ+ contention can be conducted, and (b) the “doing” of contention or engagement in contention.

The review results offer an overview of the state of the art, identifying research gaps, limitations, and opportunities. Furthermore, we outline an agenda for future comparative research in this area. Importantly, this paper contributes to increasing the visibility of LGBTQ+ issues in a still hostile public debate for both LGBTQ+ activists and researchers.

Fememe Fetal – Understanding the Representation of Women in Indian Political Memes

Mitul Joseph Koickakudy (CHRIST Deemed to be University, India)

As memes mutate and evolve, the political memes in India have mutated, drifting away from the definitions put forth by Milner (Milner, 2012). There are hybrid memes combining Screenshots from movies, Photos, Macros etc. This study tries to understand 1) the Representation of women in Memes 2) the Context in which women are placed in memes, and 3) How issues faced by Women are represented through memes.

The study takes political memes in Kerala during the Kerala (southern state in India) Assembly Election 2021. As the discussion regards political memes and communication, the method used to sample the memes is adopted (McLoughlin & Southern, 2021). For the current study, memes with explicit reference to elections only were chosen, totaling 377 collected from the declaration of the election to the day of the election. From the pool of 377 memes, memes with reference to women, memes that speak about women issues, memes with image of women will be chosen.

The study employs a three-dimension typology for analyzing Internet memes (Shifman, 2013). In the three-dimensional typology, three aspects of a meme are analysed through the lens of the three-dimensional model of content, form, and stance. Content is the idea/s and the ideology/ies conveyed by a specific text. Form, the physical formulation of the message, perceived through our senses. “stance” depicts how addressers position themselves concerning the text, its linguistic codes, the addressees, and other potential speakers.

16:15 - 17:45 – PANEL 6 (Hybrid session)

Videos on YouTube as a Learning Tool About Sexuality, Motherhood, and Upbringing by People with Intellectual Disabilities. A Collective Case Study from Spain and Poland

Ana María Rio Poncela (University of Cantabria, Spain), *Mateusz Smieszek* (Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Poland)

Information and knowledge are essential both on a macro-social scale and on a micro-social scale to create an open and socially aware society. People with intellectual disabilities may have difficulties accessing knowledge about sexuality or parenthood due to social and institutional deficiencies, stereotypes, stigmatization or social exclusion. The solutions provided by modern technologies can assist in addressing these challenges. Support organizations can utilize social media to spread valuable, reliable knowledge and become a crucial tool for informal education.

In our research, we focused on analyzing whether (or to what extent) the Internet (in particular video content on YouTube) can be considered as a tool for people with intellectual disabilities to learn about sexuality, parenthood, and upbringing. Our study combined aspects of a collective case study, netnography, qualitative content analysis, and comparative research. We used in our study purposeful sampling. To conduct our analysis, we selected YouTube videos covering the main topics and ideas relevant to our research project. We identified three main topics: sexuality, motherhood and upbringing by people with intellectual disabilities. We collected and analyzed Spanish and Polish to create a collective case study in order to answer main research questions: “What are the main features of Spanish and Polish videos on YouTube presenting topics of sexuality, motherhood, and upbringing?”, “To what extent videos on YouTube can be used by people with intellectual to gain knowledge about sexuality, motherhood, and upbringing?”, “How could the creators of videos on YouTube adjust their materials about sexuality, motherhood, and upbringing to make it accessible and valuable for people with intellectual disabilities?”.

Challenges, Issues and Perspectives of Independent Living in the Veneto Region: A Case Study Conducted Within a Cooperative in the Alta Padovana Area

Agnese Pellay (Università degli studi di Padova, Italy)

The claim of this work is to critically reflect on the policies for Independent Living in the Veneto Region, highlighting the results achieved, differences and critical issues in comparison with countries and territorial realities in which a Bottom-up Movement for Independent Living has developed, managed by people with disabilities. In particular, the case of study relating to an Independent Living project promoted by a cooperative in Alta Padovana area will be analyzed through qualitative research based on semi-structured interviews conducted with operators and beneficiaries of the service. The

good practices and limits of the project in promoting self-determination and deinstitutionalization of the people with disabilities involved will be also discussed.

Gender, Disability, Migration Background. An Intersectional Reading of Educational Contexts

Maria Giulia Pascariello (Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro, Italy)

This paper moves from some considerations that emerged during the initial phase of my doctoral project in Gender Studies at the University of Bari. The research concerns the intersection of disability, migration background and gender and focuses on the analysis of educational contexts. The ultimate goal of the project is the drafting of guidelines aimed at improving the organizational skills of public administration from the perspective of social inclusion and improving the impact generated by administrative work on communities. The relationship between migration and disability is an underrepresented topic in the international scholarly literature: the issue of disability is marginal in international migration studies, and at the same time, disability studies have often neglected the intersection of factors such as ethnicity or geographic origin. People with disabilities with a migrant background are nearly invisible socially, institutionally, and in public debate, despite being exposed to multiple processes of negative discrimination, often implicit in institutional practices. In this framework, my research questions, through an intersectional feminist approach, the role of educational and learning contexts. What is the role of educational contexts in generating representations of "diversity"? What tools exist for understanding disability in its intersection with multiple factors such as gender and migration background? Can schools be a space for communication between services, families, and social communities?

The ‘Bridgerton’ Question: Female Voices and Gender Expectations in the Regency Fiction

Paula Garcia-Rodriguez (University of Seville, Spain)

The influence that cinema and TV shows have in popular culture is undeniable. Popular culture is a reflection of society, so it was reasonable that Netflix’s series *Bridgerton* (2020) emerged as a cultural phenomenon that has conquered the audience around the world, as the creators explained that they pretended to “reflect the world that we live in today” (Jean-Phillipe). This series has gained notoriety for its visual representations and its setting in the British Regency society, but it has also brought forward debates around its approach with sensitive topics in the specific historical context. The present study aims to examine how *Bridgerton* tackles gender vulnerability, highlighting women’s struggle to find their own voices and autonomy in an age where the expectations of marriage and maternity controlled the social narrative. Through characters like Daphne, Eloise or Anthony Bridgerton, Shondaland’s series reflects how gender standards affected every character regardless of their gender. Reading this series through an intersectional feminist perspective and addressing studies such as “Men, Masculinity and Manhood Acts” by Douglas Schrock or *Becoming a Woman through Romance* by Linda K. Christian-Smith, this study sheds light upon how *Bridgerton* contributes to the speech about gender in popular culture and its relevance in the present day society.

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09:00 - 10:30 – PANEL 7 (Session entirely online)

Portraying the Gendered Image of Nursing in Electronic Media of Pakistan

Sidra Abbas (Virtual University of Pakistan, Pakistan)

The media portrays the fictional image of nurses who still perform their clinical roles as subservient in the mixed environment of hospitals. The present study uncovers the connotations depicted by media that influence nurses' perceptions of career choice and feel empowered in the provision of quality care. For this purpose, this study utilizes the theory of gender performativity and the concept of objectification as a gender lens to find a linkage between nursing social and cultural image. To achieve this, a qualitative research design was situated to dissect the phenomena through 15 in-depth interviews. Notably, a qualitative data software, NVIVO-14, was deployed as a data-manger tool in coding and pictorial narration. Considerably, the six-phase thematic analysis of Braun & Clark (2006) has been applied to analyze the study subject's points of view. The result generated three major themes such as media constantly broadcasts a stereotypical and negative image of nurses that overlooks a person's intellectual abilities; female nurses are symbolized as handmaidens of doctors and pleasure sources for their sexualized gazes due to inaccurate images; electronic media has portrayed an inappropriate image, and delivering discourteous dialogues and commercializing nurses as making medical errors. To conclude, this study has implications for the existing body of knowledge and practice especially for the nursing community. This significant study could be used as a tool for positive dissemination through media to remove stereotypes about nursing, which would help the government start community health nursing in Pakistan.

The film “Margarita with a Straw” (2014): Linking Disability, Accessibility and Sexuality

Baby Rizwana N V (Independent Researcher, Malappuram, India)

The Indian film industry lags behind in its portrayal of disabled characters, often depicting them as hopeless and melancholic. However, in 2014, there was a significant shift with the release of a Hindi movie titled "Margarita with a Straw," directed by Shonali Bose and starring Kalki Koechlin. The film tells the story of Laila Kapoor, a young woman with cerebral palsy, her family dynamics in India, and her journey to America for her undergraduate studies. "Margarita with a Straw" received exceptional acclaim on international platforms due to its innovative approach and sensitive portrayal of disability. In a country where traditional views of disability are often tied to karma, this film breathed fresh life into three key aspects: redefining disability, exploring disability and inclusion, and addressing disability and sexuality.

The first section of my paper delves into how the movie challenges conventional notions of disability. It highlights how the film treats Laila as a complete individual—a person capable of making her own decisions, aspiring for independence, and standing up for her beliefs. Throughout the movie, there is no trace of the traditional karmic view of disability.

The second section of the paper explores the theme of sexuality in the film. Indian society tends to desexualize individuals with disabilities, but "Margarita with a Straw" breaks this norm. The film portrays Laila's exploration of her sexuality, including her realization of bisexuality, while examining her family's disapproval within the context of disability and sexuality.

The third section of the paper focuses on the accessibility aspect. It conducts a comparative analysis of the physical accessibility challenges Laila faces in India versus America. The film is noteworthy for its portrayal of disability without resorting to stereotypes, marking a ground-breaking moment in Hindi cinema.

Seeing the Gender of Disabled Bodies: Rights Protection and Social Support Issues for Disabled Women – Evidence from China

Yiqi Hu (College of Humanities and Development Studies, China Agricultural University, China)

In China, there are more than 3.7 million people with spinal cord injury, and they will spend their whole life in wheelchairs, not only suffer from long-term problems of secondary diseases, but also face great problems in depression, social discrimination, and barrier-free travel. It is worth mentioning that women with spinal cord injury face more challenges due to the influence of natural body structure and social stereotypes. Based on the in-depth interview and participatory observation of them, we concluded that the outstanding problems are as follows: in daily life nursing, they may not only need care, but also be caregivers in the family and unable to get professional nursing services; In terms of reproduction, they may have the desire to be mothers, but because of the label of "disability", they are suppressed by society and cannot meet their emotional needs; In terms of career development, their dual identities as women and disabled make it easier for them to be regarded as "trouble" and discriminated against in job hunting, entrepreneurship and even working process, so they cannot realize their value. In view of the above problems, this study focuses on a more inclusive and perfect social support system. On the one hand, it explores the role of non-governmental organizations and communities in the construction of social support networks for women with spinal cord injury; On the other hand, the development of "social inclusion" social policies to guide the elimination of social exclusion faced by women with spinal cord injury.

Disability between Vulnerability and Empowerment: Inspirations for Feminist Social Research

Lyuboslava Kostova (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria)

This article deals with the concept of disability as an inner source of inspiration and creative capabilities due to inherent human vulnerability. The focus emphasizes three main points: disability, inspiration and self-fulfillment. Is it possible to use your own disadvantages to create a better and more honest version of yourself? Feminist philosophy gives us such perspective because in its roots it is all about embodiment. Eva F. Kittay and Adrienne Ash are just some of the examples. What is really unique about feminism is neither its political correctness, nor the so-called 'cancel culture' of today. The real advantage of feminist research is its own situatedness, engagement and attachment. If the object of science is to grasp the essence of subjects independently of knowers, then one must distinguish sharply the knower from the known. However, when the objects of inquiry are knowers themselves, this dichotomy rules out the possibility that knowers' self-understandings help constitute knowers' perspectives and intellectual approaches.

Thus, for many feminists their own research is a form of deeper understanding of the social structures, the important actors, and basically – of themselves. Feminist inquiries can be a source of both healing and empowerment, especially in the cases where female social researchers (have a connection) with disability and willingness to accept their own vulnerability. For me, this perspective is extremely important and precious.

11:00 – 12:30 – PANEL 8 (Session entirely online)

Evolving Gender Stereotypes in the Digital Age: An Analysis of Viral Content on TikTok and Instagram Reels

Swastika Suresh Bhat (Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Dubai, UAE)

This study explores the gender stereotypes shared in the form of viral content on widely used social media platforms such as TikTok and Instagram Reels. This study also provides a better understanding of the effect of such content on youth and how gender stereotypes have evolved over time. The primary objectives of this study are: 1) To examine the types of viral content contributing to gender stereotypes; 2) To learn how this content affects young people's beliefs.

The hypothesis states that exposure to content promoting gender stereotypes on TikTok and Instagram Reels will significantly influence the minds of the younger generation, leading them to mistake these stereotypes as gender norms.

The study analyses viral content that becomes a trend, spreads globally, and urges active users to create imitations. It is categorized into theme, message imparted, and the stereotypes they create. The focus group of the research is Gen Z, on whom the impact is studied through surveys and/or in-depth interviews.

This research adds to our understanding of how gender stereotypes are evolving and affecting young minds in the digital age. By focusing on TikTok and Instagram reels, which are platforms used globally, especially by the younger generation, this study aims to emphasize the need for change in the type of content and the way gender is portrayed and perceived in the digital era.

Sludge Content and Its Impact on the Gen Z Attention Span

Parth Joshi (Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Dubai, UAE)

In recent years, there has been a drastic change in the content over social media, which has also been affecting the attention span of the newer generation i.e. Gen Z. Platforms such as TikTok have algorithms that lean towards promoting short-form and sludge content, which attracts more attention (views) over content that is approximately over a minute long. Such content includes different elements that capture the attention of the Gen Z users, while also being quite short in its overall duration. The constant consumption of this content has brought a change in how content is created and distributed across different platforms.

The Impact of Using Tik Tok Beauty Filters on the Body Image/Self-Esteem of University Students

Evelin Barney (Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Dubai, UAE)

With the rise in popularity of social media apps such as Tik tok, Snapchat, Instagram from youth to adults, we also observe a simultaneous increase in the number of people relying on it's in-app features to tag, edit and enhance videos before uploading them on these platforms. In the case of Tik tok, Many of its users heavily depend on features such as beauty filters or tools to edit or enhance facial features as they allow them to post videos of themselves looking seemingly flawless and beautiful based on their cultures beauty standards. Therefore eliminating self limiting feelings of being

inadequate, unattractive and unaccepted by the in-app community. But the constant usage and exposure to these beauty effects or filters blurs the line between reality and what's fake. It distorts perception, promotes usage of such beauty filters and tools, facilitates in glorifying already existing toxic beauty standards, and as a result negatively effects users body image/self-esteem. Thus, this research aims to study the harmful impact of using beauty filters on body image/self-esteem among university students and examine the differences in body image/self-esteem between students who use Tik tok beauty filters and those who don't. For the research, a sample group of university students aged 17 to 24 are to be studied through survey method and indept-interviews.

Cinematic Influence on Gender Stereotypes: A Comprehensive Analysis of Contemporary Hollywood Cinema and Its Effect on Young Adults' Perceptions

Muskan Vinod Bhatia (Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Dubai, UAE)

This research paper studies how gender stereotype is portrayed in contemporary Hollywood cinema and understands its influence on the perceptions and beliefs of young adults. The paper utilizes the Male Gaze theory as a theoretical framework to analyze how movies have historically reinforced gender stereotypes, thereby significantly molding the way audiences perceive gender dynamics on the big screen. Through primary research methods, the research paper brings insights of how gender stereotypes shape the culture of the society and builds deep-rooted beliefs and values which ultimately affects the future of the generations. This research paper also explores the reactions of different age groups to these stereotypes movie scenes which gives us valuable insights into understanding the opinions of the young audiences. Additionally, the study conducts an in-depth analysis of the recurring themes in the recent movies that perpetuate gender stereotypes, therefore delivering a comprehensive assessment of narrative patterns in contemporary filmmaking.

13:00 - 14:30 – PANEL 9 (Session entirely online)

Identifying with the Main Character of a Fantasy Story: How Disability Is Discussed on Booktube. The Case Study of Sarah-Jane Bird

Clara Sánchez-Rebato Valiente (Complutense University of Madrid, Spain)

Booktube is an online community where readers, normally teens and young adults share their love for reading through their thematic YouTube channels (Lluch, 2017), where they make recommendations and book reviews in video form. From the theoretical perspective, this community is influenced by the participatory culture and its principles, especially visible in the communication dynamics produced on the platform (Jenkins et al., 2015). This proposal aims to study the verbal communication of this type of video, exploring if literary influencers feel identification with the main characters of the books they recommend, specifically if this identification can happen with characters with disabilities, and if so, how the booktuber expresses it. A case study methodology approach is used, analysing the production of Sarah-Jane Bird, owner of the channel TheBookLife, and in particular her review of a story whose main character was explicitly disabled, A curse so dark and lonely by Brigid Kemmerer. A multimodal discourse analysis, studied through social semiotics' lenses, as well as a semi-structured interview were conducted. The results show that booktubers identify with characters who have similar life experiences than theirs, but, at the same time, they would only point out disability as a relevant aspect of the review if the influencers themselves had enough knowledge about

the topic. This way of approaching identification shows how booktubers tend to highlight honesty and truthfulness as important values for the reviews, not only for themselves, but to ensure certain topics are discussed by those who are affected by them.

Surveilling the Boundaries of a Black Man's Sanity

Natalie Byfield (St. John's University, USA)

New York State, a politically liberal state in the USA, uses Kendra's Law which allows for the involuntary outpatient commitment of people with diagnosed mental illnesses. This law supports a state-run system of outpatient care, described as the highest level of care outside the hospital, and maintains patients in this monitored system, even when they want to get independent care. Much of this inpatient/outpatient care for people with illnesses like schizophrenia are singularly focused on their mental health status, not on other features of their identity like their racial and class backgrounds. Nor does care incorporate an understanding of their whole selves, like their talents. This paper is a case study examining the artistic contributions of one such patient, an African American male artist, who was also my son, Kenya Sheppard. His racial identity made him more easily labeled as violent and decreased the likelihood of an acknowledgement of his artistic talents as a way to support his recovery. Regardless, Kenya used his music, art, and writing to sustain his identity as a whole person, as a way to critique and survive the mental health care system, and as a way to help people going through similar experiences. This paper uses Kenya's own writings, art, and music, as well as textual analyses of this work to interrogate the efficacy of a system that ignores a person's whole self and to reveal how he used the arts as a vehicle of support for people who face mental health challenges.

How LGBTQ+ Became "A National Security Threat": Turkey's Anti-LGBTQ+ Rhetoric

Ilayda Ustel (The Ohio State University, USA)

Over the last several years, Turkish government's anti-LGBTQI+ stance has become more prominent through the statements of the president and the government officials, legislation passed, and the actions taken by state agencies. This hatred is framed through a "family values" rhetoric. Through the conceptualization of "family" as a sacred and essential part of Turkish society, any other form of family or non-heteronormative existence is labeled as harmful to the social structure. On September 18, 2022, the first anti-LGBTQ+ "Great Family Meeting" took place in Istanbul with thousands of people claiming to have come together to oppose the "LGBT propaganda" to "protect families and children," and to demand a ban on LGBTQ+ groups and activity from the state. The second of these meetings took place on September 17, 2023, ahead of which, the organizers circulated a video promoting the rally containing images from past LGBTQ+ Pride marches in Turkey. This video was approved as a public service announcement to be broadcast on TV channels. In this presentation, I will be looking into the state's and protesters' use of media (both mainstream media and social media channels) to disseminate the pro-family and anti-LGBTQ+ discourse as a way of marking which bodies are disposable and which are worth protecting, and the criminalization of LGBTQ+ groups through a "national security" discourse, through an analysis of multimedia material produced and distributed by the government and the protesters as my primary material, as well as secondary material such as articles and social media posts written by LGBTQ+ activists and scholars.

Feminist Translation into Spanish of Sexist Scenes Characterized by the Male Gaze of LIU Cixin's the Three-Body Trilogy

Ying Tan (Beijing Language and Culture University, China)

Liu Cixin's *The Three-Body Trilogy* can be considered the best-known Chinese science fiction novel in all over the world. However, beyond its success, it has aroused a great deal of controversy in terms of sexism. For example, in the original Chinese version we can quite often find sexist scenes characterized by the male gaze. In a world dominated by sexual inequality, the pleasure of looking is divided into active/male and passive/female. The former is determinant and projects its fantasies on the delectable female figures, molded according to the male gaze; on the contrary, women, sexual objects looked at and exhibited at the same time, traditionally play an exhibitionist role with their appearance in order to provoke a strong visual and erotic impact among the male holders of the gaze, being subjected to a to-be-looked-at-ness.

In the translation studies, the interventionist feminist translation allows the translators to intervene when working with a sexist source text, and its goal is to have a target text free of sexism. Although the translators of this novel are not feminists, we have observed a difference about the depictions of the male gaze between the Chinese version and the Spanish one. Therefore, we are interested in analyzing this difference from the perspective of the feminist translation in order to find out how the translators deal with this problem and what effects the Chinese original text and the Spanish translation have.